

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

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LITERATURE REVIEW

Modern scientific views on the management of industrial zones and the improvement of their competitiveness are reflected in Michael Porter's works *The Competitive Advantage of Nations* (1990) and *Clusters and the New Economics of Competition* (1998). Porter developed the cluster theory and scientifically substantiated that the close territorial concentration of enterprises accelerates innovation, reduces production costs, and increases investment attractiveness [1].

The report *Industrial Parks for Inclusive and Sustainable Industrial Development* (2019), published by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), analyzes the importance of industrial zones in sustainable economic development. The study highlights the role of industrial parks in promoting innovative development, technology transfer, and job creation.

UNIDO's report *Industrial Parks and Economic Transformation* (2021) examines the experiences of China, South Korea, Vietnam, and Singapore and concludes that the success of industrial zones depends on modern management systems, digitalization, and innovative infrastructure.

The OECD report *Industrial Policy for the Sustainable Development Goals* (2020) emphasizes the need to introduce green economy principles, environmental sustainability, and digital technologies into the management of industrial zones.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In conducting this study, several scientific methods of economic analysis were applied. The research employed statistical data analysis, comparative analysis, a systematic approach, logical generalization, and economic analysis methods. The impact of regional industrial zones on economic development was examined based on scientific sources and statistical data. In addition, international experience in the organization and management of industrial zones was analyzed within the framework of the study.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Chinese Experience. China is one of the most successful countries in the world in the development of industrial zones. The country has attracted large-scale investment through the creation of special economic zones and industrial parks. The management of industrial zones is carried out through cooperation between central and local authorities.

The main advantages of the Chinese experience include strong state support, modern infrastructure, export-oriented production, and the introduction of innovative technologies.

The first special economic zones in China were established in 1980, among which Shenzhen, Zhuhai, Shantou, and Xiamen were of particular importance. These zones provided investors with tax incentives, customs preferences, and simplified administrative procedures. As a result, large amounts of foreign investment were attracted within a short period, and industrial production increased significantly.

One of the important aspects of the Chinese experience is the active participation of the state in the development of industrial zones. While the central government creates the legal framework for the establishment of industrial zones, local authorities carry out the tasks of infrastructure construction, investor attraction, and coordination of enterprise activities. Such a two-tier management system contributes to the effective functioning of industrial zones [2].

In China, the management of industrial zones is organized according to the "one-stop shop" principle. Investors can receive land allocation, construction permits, registration, and other services through a single center. This reduces administrative barriers and significantly lowers the cost of doing business. Another important feature of Chinese industrial zones is their development based on the principle of clustering. Each industrial zone specializes in a specific industry or direction. For example, specialized clusters have been created for electronics, automotive manufacturing, chemistry, information technology, and mechanical engineering. This has enabled the development of cooperative relations between enterprises, the reduction of logistics costs, and the acceleration of innovation exchange.

South Korean Experience. In South Korea, industrial zones are developed according to the principle of industrial clustering. Close cooperation has been established between enterprises, research centers, and universities. As a result, the production and export of innovative products have increased significantly.

The policy of supporting small and medium-sized businesses in South Korea is also closely linked to industrial zones. Small enterprises are integrated into large industrial clusters and become an important link in the supply chain. This contributes to increasing production efficiency and strengthening the value chain.

Developed transport and logistics infrastructure is also one of the important advantages of South Korean industrial zones. Industrial zones are integrated with seaports, railways, and highways, which allows export operations to be carried out quickly and efficiently.

Ha-Joon Chang, who studied the South Korean experience, emphasizes that the success of industrial policy is based on strategic state intervention and long-term planning. In his view, industrial zones enabled the country to overcome technological backwardness and become a high-income economy.

Research shows that the success of South Korean industrial zones is determined by the following factors: strategic industrial policy of the state, integration of science and industry, high-tech production, cooperation between large corporations and small businesses, developed logistics and export infrastructure, an innovative ecosystem, and investment in research and development.

In conclusion, the South Korean experience shows that small industrial zones can be formed not only as production areas, but also as centers of innovative development. This experience has important practical significance for Uzbekistan in modernizing industrial zones, developing innovative clusters, and introducing elements of the digital economy [3].

German Experience. In Germany, industrial zones are aimed at supporting small and medium-sized businesses. Engineering services, logistics centers, and business incubators operate in regional industrial parks. Public-private partnership mechanisms are widely used in this process.

The concept of industrial zone development in Germany has historically been closely linked to the principles of the regional economy and the social market economy. In particular, the system of small and medium-sized enterprises, known as the “Mittelstand,” is the main foundation of industrial zones. These enterprises are located in industrial zones and have become an important link in large production chains.

One of the main principles of managing industrial zones in Germany is the implementation of regional economic policy based on a federal structure. Each federal state (Bundesland) independently develops its own industrial policy and actively participates in the development of industrial zones. This system serves to reduce economic disparities between regions.

The mechanism of public-private partnership (PPP) is widely used in the development of industrial zones. While the state develops infrastructure, the private sector carries out production and innovation activities. This helps to use resources efficiently and reduce investment risks.

Another important feature of German industrial zones is their high level of specialization. For example, automotive and mechanical engineering clusters are developed in Baden-Württemberg, while electronics and aerospace industries are concentrated in Bavaria. This specialization increases production efficiency and strengthens global competitiveness.

In industrial zones, science and production are highly integrated. Universities, research centers, and technology parks work closely with industrial enterprises. For example, the Fraunhofer Society plays an important role in the development of applied research and industrial innovation in Germany. This organization, in cooperation with industrial enterprises, develops new technologies and introduces them into production.

Logistics and transport infrastructure are among the main advantages of German industrial zones. The country is located in the center of Europe, and its developed highways, railway networks, and river transport ensure the effective operation of industrial zones. In particular, the ports of Hamburg and Bremen play an important role in export operations.

Michael Porter, who studied the German experience, substantiated the relationship between territorial specialization and competitiveness in cluster theory, and German industrial zones are considered a practical expression of this theory [4].

The analysis shows that German industrial zones have achieved success due to the following main factors: a strong federal and regional management system, an economy based on small and medium-sized businesses, high specialization and clustering, integration of science and production, public-private partnership mechanisms, principles of environmental sustainability and “green industry,” and developed logistics infrastructure.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

First, the experience of foreign countries confirms that small industrial zones are an effective tool for regional economic development.

Second, the success of industrial zones depends on developed infrastructure, a favorable investment environment, and an effective management system.

Third, the introduction of innovative technologies and digital management mechanisms is an important factor in increasing the efficiency of industrial zones.

Based on the study, the following recommendations were developed:

Introduce digital management platforms in small industrial zones.

Develop industrial clusters and cooperative relations between enterprises.

Expand public-private partnership mechanisms.

Support innovative and export-oriented projects.

Introduce a comprehensive system of indicators for assessing the efficiency of industrial zones.

The practical implementation of these recommendations will help increase the competitiveness of small industrial zones in Uzbekistan, expand investment volumes, and accelerate regional economic development.

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